

Polyglycerol functionalization of ZnO nanoparticles for stable hydrosol in physiological media[†]

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Manuscript received 01 November 2011, accepted 03 November 2011

Abstract : ZnO nanoparticles (30~200 nm) were covalently functionalized with multibranched polyglycerol (PG) by ring-opening polymerization. The PG-functionalized ZnO nanoparticles (ZnO-PG) were characterized by FTIR, TG, and elemental analysis. TG revealed that ZnO-PG includes the PG functionality with 5.8% in weight. The PG layer made the ZnO nanoparticles soluble not only in pure water, but also in physiological media. This result may accelerate the applications of ZnO nanoparticles in biology and medicine.

Keywords : Nanoparticles, polymerization, solubilization, zinc oxide.

Introduction

ZnO nanoparticles are of great interest in the field of nanoscience and nanotechnology owing to their wide availability and unique property¹⁻³. ZnO nanoparticles have been used as additives in cosmetics for many years due to their inherent ability to absorb UV light. Their biomedical applications have recently been explored for disinfection⁴, cell labeling⁵, drug delivery⁶, and biosensors⁷. In recent study, ZnO nanoparticles showed inherent cytotoxicity against cancer cells *in vitro* because of the reactive oxygen species generated by ZnO nanoparticles⁸.

In biomedical applications such as imaging probe, cancer drug, and drug carrier, the nanoparticles should form stable hydrosol in physiological media⁹. Therefore, surface modification of the nanoparticles is required to impart hydrophilicity to them. Physisorption of triethylene glycol molecules¹⁰ and covalent functionalization with polyethylene glycol (PEG)¹¹ and poly(amido amine) (PAMAM) dendrons¹² have been reported in the case of the ZnO nanoparticles. However, simpler and more efficient modification is desired to prepare soluble ZnO nanoparticles. Quite recently, we have developed methodology of polyglycerol (PG) functionalization on the sur-

face of nanodiamonds to achieve very high solubility in physiological media. Such high solubility enabled us to separate the nanodiamonds according to their sizes through size exclusion chromatography¹³. In this study, we have extended the methodology to the surface functionalization of ZnO nanoparticles. The high hydrophilicity and multi-branched structure of PG render the ZnO nanoparticles soluble and stable in physiological media, paving the way for the biomedical applications of ZnO nanoparticles.

Results and discussion

PG-functionalized ZnO nanoparticles (ZnO-PG) were prepared as shown in Scheme 1. The hydroxyl (-OH) groups on the ZnO surface, which were confirmed by IR (Fig. 1), are considered to initiate the ring-opening polymerization of glycidol at high temperature. After removal of the PG without ZnO core (free PG)¹³ by washing with water (see the Experimental), the ZnO-PG was characterized with IR (Fig. 1), elemental analysis (Table 1), and TG (Fig. 2). In the IR spectra, the new absorptions are appeared at 2900, 1100 and 500 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C-H, C-O-C, and Zn-O stretching, respectively, sug-

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Scheme 1. Synthesis of ZnO-PG through the ring-opening polymerization of glycidol.

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of ZnO nanoparticles and ZnO-PG as solids.

Table 1. Elemental analysis of ZnO nanoparticle and ZnO-PG

Element	ZnO nanoparticle (wt. %)	ZnO-PG (wt. %)
C	0.27	2.15
H	0.53	0.87

gesting that PG functionality was constructed on the ZnO surface. Results of the elemental analysis and TG support the above conclusion of the synthesis of ZnO-PG. The contents of the carbon and hydrogen increase after the functionalization (Table 1), indicating the participation of organic functionality on the ZnO nanoparticles. The TG shows that there exist burnable and unburnable components in the particles, which correspond to the PG func-

tionality and ZnO core. The weight ratio of the PG layer and the ZnO core is determined to be 5.8 : 94.2.

The sizes and the shapes of the nanoparticles were determined by scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) before and after PG functionalization. As shown in Fig. 3a, as-received ZnO nanoparticles showed irregular shape with particle size of 30–200 nm. After PG modification, the soluble nanoparticles exhibited rounder shape and smaller size (30–140 nm) as shown in Fig. 3b. This is probably because larger and/or non-spherical particles were not soluble in water and were precipitated out.

The synthesized ZnO-PG was dissolved in the aqueous solvents. ZnO nanoparticles exhibited almost no solubility in pure water and thoroughly precipitated in phos-

Fig. 2. TG profiles of ZnO nanoparticles and ZnO-PG under nitrogen and air.

Fig. 3. STEM images of (a) ZnO nanoparticles and (b) ZnO-PG. Scale bars represent 100 nm.

phate buffered saline (PBS) (Fig. 4a). On the other hand, ZnO-PG was solubilized not only in pure water, but also in PBS (Fig. 4b). After standing overnight, the superna-

tant was desalinated by dialysis and the concentration of ZnO-PG was determined to be about 0.1 mg/mL.

In summary, ZnO nanoparticles were covalently functionalized with hyperbranched PG through ring-opening multibranching polymerization of glycidol at high temperature. The highly hydrophilic PG layer enabled ZnO-PG soluble in PBS. Since this is the second example after PG-functionalized nanodiamond, the methodology of the PG functionalization is believed to be widely applicable to other nanoparticles to be soluble in physiological media.

Experimental

Materials : ZnO powder with diameter of 30~200 nm was purchased from Aldrich. Glycidol purchased from Kanto Chemical Co., Ltd was dried over 4 Å molecular sieves prior to use.

Characterizations : STEM was performed on a JEOL JSM-7500F field emission scanning electron microscope, operating at 25 kV accelerating voltage for TEM model.

Fig. 4. Photographs of (a) ZnO nanoparticles and (b) ZnO-PG in PBS after standing overnight at room temperature.

All samples for electron microscopy were prepared by evaporating one drop (~ 10 μL) of samples on ultrathin carbon-coated copper grids. FTIR spectral measurements were conducted using IR Prestige-21 (Shimadzu Co.). Samples were prepared by drop-coating of suspension to form a thin film on plate, and then dried in vacuo overnight. TG was carried out by a Q-50 analyzer (TA instruments) with a heating rate of $20^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ under a nitrogen flow or an air flow (60 mL min^{-1}). Elemental analysis was performed on a Vario MICRO-cube (Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH).

Preparation of ZnO-PG : The suspension of as-received ZnO powder (50 mg) in glycidol (10 mL) was bath-sonicated at 25°C for 30 min and the resulting well-dispersed suspension was magnetically stirred at 140°C under argon atmosphere for 20 h. After cooling down to room temperature, the resulting white gel was diluted with water (60 mL) in an ultrasonic bath and the precipitates were recovered after centrifugation at 50800 g for 20 min. This washing process was repeated 3 times more to remove the free PG. The resulting suspension was lyophilized to give a white solid (54.2 mg).

Acknowledgement

This work was financially supported by Science and Technology Incubation Program in Advanced Region (JST), Industrial Technology Research Grant Program (NEDO), and Grant-in-Aid for Challenging Exploratory Research (JSPS).

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